

Parameterised Physics-Informed Neural Networks for Neutron Diffusion: Initial case study

Hasnain Gulzar ^{1*}, Dzianis Litskevich¹, Seddon Atkinson², Brendon Perry², Anna Detkina¹,
Abdo Ez Aldeen¹

¹School of Engineering, University of Liverpool, L69 3GH, UK;

²United Kingdom National Nuclear Laboratory (UKNNL), Warrington, WA36 6A

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ABSTRACT

Physics Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) are a growing field in the study of solvers for partial differential equations (PDEs). To showcase the capabilities of PINNs, the neutron diffusion PDE is modelled for a one-dimensional, one-group, fixed-source geometry. The results compared to a finite difference solver showed a mean relative difference of 0.3%. In PINNs, however, the models are trained on fixed material parameters, such as the absorption cross-section and the diffusion coefficient. This introduces a major limitation of PINNs as they must be retrained whenever these constants are changed for new predictions. To address this, parametric models are needed that allow users to specify material properties at the inference stage rather than before training. Accordingly, this paper provides a preliminary parametric study on a one-dimensional non-multiplying neutron diffusion equation, demonstrating that PINNs can generalise to previously unseen material properties without the need to retrain. The model was trained over a specified range of physical parameters and then tested using randomly selected, unseen cross-sections within this range, achieving a mean relative difference of 0.39% across 100 cases. Next the same model was assessed on an additional 156 randomly assigned parameters beyond the training range and this showed a mean relative difference of 0.47% compared to the reference solver. The results highlight the potential of PINNs to serve as fast, and mesh-free solvers in reactor physics.

Keywords: Neutron Diffusion Equation, Neural Network, PINNs, Parameterisation

1. INTRODUCTION

The neutron transport equation provides a comprehensive understanding of the neutronics inside the reactor core; however, simplifications are often needed due to the complex nature of the geometry and the physical phenomena involved. The neutron diffusion equation is a consequence of such approximations and provides a much more manageable equation to solve. Traditionally, diffusion problems are solved on a discretised domain using established numerical methods such as the finite difference method (FDM), finite element method (FEM), and finite volume method (FVM), as well as nodal and coarse-mesh approaches.

These methods require a mesh with spatial discretisation and the solution is then computed at finite set of grid points or cells. Achieving higher accuracy typically requires mesh refinement, which increases the numbers of cells and therefore raises memory usage and runtime. Further, while such approaches are efficient for fixed problem configurations, a key limitation is limited reusability, since changes in geometry, material properties, boundary conditions or material parameters necessitate remeshing and resolving the system from scratch. In recent years, advances in machine learning have led to the development of algorithms like neural networks being utilised in many scientific fields. The power of these algorithms arise from the fact that neural networks have been proven to be universal approximators,

*pshgulza@liverpool.ac.uk

meaning that given sufficient architecture and a non-polynomial function, any continuous function can be learnt to a desired accuracy.

However, plain neural networks rely heavily on data to learn the mapping relationship between the inputs and the outputs, and in many instances, such data may be difficult to obtain, impractical to generate, be safeguarded under strict security, or may simply not exist, particularly for new concepts which fall outside the existing data realm. This led to the field of scientific machine learning (SciML), which attempts to combine the learning capabilities of neural network with the theoretical principles to solve partial differential equations (PDEs). One growing approach in this area is Physics Informed Neural Network (PINN).

PINNs provide a mesh-free alternative by representing the solution as a continuous function and enforcing the governing equation and boundary conditions (BC) through the loss function at collocation points, thereby avoiding explicit grid-based discretisation. This can be advantageous for parametric studies, where a single trained model may be reused across varying inputs without regenerating a mesh, potentially reducing computational cost and runtime once training is complete. This paper focuses on applying the PINN framework to a one-dimensional slab problem and subsequently extend the approach to parameterisation for demonstrating the model's ability in making accurate predictions for new material properties without requiring retraining.

PINNs were first introduced by Raissi et al [1] as a framework that embeds partial differential equations directly into a neural network the loss function. Rather than relying on data, PINNs enforce the physical laws to guide the learning process. Since then, several extensions have been proposed, including Variational PINNs, which minimise the variational form of the governing PDE [2], eXtended PINNs, which partition the computational domain into multiple sub-networks so each learn within its own subdomain [3], and conservative PINNs, which builds on domain decomposition by enforcing conservation laws across the interface boundaries [4]. Although these approaches use different algorithms, their core principle remains same, that the network must satisfy the underlying PDEs at inference. While physical knowledge alone can provide reasonable predictions, hybrid approaches can be combined with empirical data to further strengthen the model's robustness. Whereas purely data-driven models are often difficult to interpret, the PINN approach mitigates this 'black box' nature through its scientific backing.

PINNs have been successfully applied across a wide spectrum of scientific and engineering fields, including the neutron diffusion problem. Xu et al. [5] introduced a deep learning framework for multi-dimensional neutron diffusion, proposing novel boundary condition treatments. Wang et al. [4] enhanced this approach through conservative formulations and explicit boundary condition enforcement for improved consistency. Yang et al. [6] solved 1D and 2D neutron diffusion problems using PINNs and later integrated data-driven methods to predict the effective multiplication factor. Elhareef and Wu [7] conducted a pilot study exploring the feasibility of applying PINNs to reactor physics, in both single and multiple energy groups. Yong and Zhou [8] further advanced the method by directly addressing eigenvalue formulations. More recently, Yang et al. [9] employed a physics-constrained network for discontinuous interface problems, resulting in a higher accuracy across heterogenous systems.

To the best of the author's knowledge, there are not many studies that apply parameterisation to the neutron diffusion equation. One example identified is the work of Xie et al. [10], which considers a single, arbitrary selected parameter range and evaluates performance by comparing only one configuration against a reference solver. In contrast, the present work uses reactor-relevant material properties generated using OpenMC and varies both the diffusion coefficient and the absorption cross-section over physically consistent ranges. The model is then validated against a reference solver across 256 distinct material configurations, enabling a more comprehensive error assessment than a single-case comparison.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Neutron diffusion theory

Following reactor theory, the fixed-source neutron diffusion equation is given in (1) and is complemented by the vacuum (zero-incoming) boundary condition in (2).

$$-D \frac{\partial^2 \phi(x)}{\partial x^2} + \Sigma_a \phi(x) = S \quad (1)$$

where $\phi(x)$ is the neutron flux, Σ_a is the absorption cross-section, S is the external source, and D is the diffusion coefficient.

$$\pm D \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2} \phi \quad (2)$$

2.2. PINNs

The core idea of PINNs is to embed the governing laws directly into the loss function of a neural network. Suppose a network is trained to approximate the neutron flux:

$$NN(x) = \phi(x) \quad (3)$$

Using automatic differentiation on (3), the PDE in (1) can be reconstructed. Therefore, the PDE residual at any collocation point x becomes:

$$R_{PDE} = -D \frac{\partial^2 (x)}{\partial x^2} + \Sigma_a NN(x) - S \quad (4)$$

Similarly, the BC in (2) can be constructed to give the total loss as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \underbrace{\|R_{PDE}\|^2}_{\text{Physics}} + \underbrace{\|R_{BC}\|^2}_{\text{Boundary}} + \underbrace{\|R_{\text{Interface}}\|^2}_{\text{Interface}} \quad (5)$$

Training the network on (1) and minimising the losses in (5) will then push the model towards satisfying the neutron diffusion equation.

Figure 1. The overall workflow of PINNs

Figure 1 shows the computational workflow of PINNs. Spatial coordinates along with the material parameters are passed to the fully connected neural network, and the output is assumed to approximate the neutron flux $\phi(x)$. Automatic differentiation is applied to the output to compute the first and second derivative of the flux, which are then substituted into the governing equations. The corresponding residual terms are combined into a single loss function, which is minimised through a gradient descent-based optimisation algorithm. The process updates the neural network's learned parameters until the training iterations are completed, or a convergence residual threshold criteria is met.

2.3. Problem formulation

Figure 2 depicts the problem consisting of a one-dimensional, UO_2 slab with the left and right surfaces constrained by the zero incoming flux boundary condition.

Figure 2. The one-dimensional problem domain with the OpenMC generated material properties

The accuracy of neutron diffusion calculations depends directly on the quality of the underlying material data. The one-group cross-section data for this study was generated through OpenMC by constructing a model of a typical 17x17 pressurised water reactor's fuel assembly, with guide tubes, in order to introduce heterogeneity as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The 17x17 PWR fuel assembly used to generate homogenised one-group cross-sections

The resulting multi-group cross-sections were collapsed into a single energy group through flux weight-

ing. These flux-weighted, assembly-homogenised, one-group cross sections were then used as the material input for the simplified one-dimensional slab problem.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Standard PINNs

Figure 4 depicts the PINNs flux distribution against the finite difference reference solver. The relative difference was found to be 0.88%. The errors were the largest on the boundaries of the slab, which can be expected because the flux exhibits sharp gradient changes in these regions. Such behaviour is challenging for both PINNs and finite-difference solvers to capture accurately. The boundary related errors can be reduced further, however, the behaviour of flux at the very edges is typically not of primary interest. There was also no systematic hyperparameter turning performed as the hyperparameters adopted were taken from commonly found values in literature for machine learning problems. The overall agreement justified moving on to the parameterisation problem.

Figure 4. 1D PINNs solution compared with the reference finite difference solver

3.2. Parameterised PINNs

The second problem explores parameterisation of the diffusion equation by revisiting the problem shown in Figure 2 but with variable material coefficients. Unlike the previous fixed-coefficient PINN, the model here is trained across a range of parameters. The isotopic composition was kept constant, and physically consistent parameter ranges were generated by varying the effective material density during cross-section generation in OpenMC. This altered the macroscopic cross-sections and diffusion coefficients. The resulting sample ranges were $\Sigma_a \in [0.012, 0.03] \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $D \in [0.40, 0.79] \text{ cm}$.

Two inference scenarios were considered: Case 1 evaluates parameter values that lie within the training range of the PDE coefficients, while Case 2 considers values outside this range. Figure 5 shows the distribution of absorption cross-sections and diffusion coefficients used during inference. The grey central region denotes the 100 parameter pairs within the trained range, whereas the 156 pairs that lie outside the range are used to assess the model's ability to generalise beyond the training domain. These out of range samples corresponds to relative changes of 5%, 10% and 15% with respect to the boundary of the trained parameter regions. Together, these cases enable both the interpolation and extrapolation capabilities of PINNs to be evaluated.

0.0170	0.0163	0.0155	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0148	0.0155	0.0163	0.0170
0.5936	0.6205	0.6501	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.6826	0.3236	0.3089	0.2955
0.0163	0.0155	0.0148	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0141	0.0148	0.0155	0.0163
0.6205	0.6488	0.6796	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.7136	0.3383	0.3229	0.3089
0.0155	0.0148	0.0142	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0135	0.0142	0.0148	0.0155
0.6501	0.6796	0.7120	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.7476	0.3544	0.3383	0.3236
0.0148	0.0141	0.0135	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0128	0.0135	0.0141	0.0148
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0169	0.0161	0.0154	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0147	0.0154	0.0161	0.0169
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0190	0.0182	0.0173	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0165	0.0173	0.0182	0.0190
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0211	0.0202	0.0193	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0183	0.0193	0.0202	0.0211
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0232	0.0222	0.0212	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0202	0.0212	0.0222	0.0232
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0253	0.0242	0.0231	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0220	0.0231	0.0242	0.0253
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0274	0.0262	0.0250	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0238	0.0250	0.0262	0.0274
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0295	0.0282	0.0269	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0257	0.0269	0.0282	0.0295
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0316	0.0302	0.0289	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0275	0.0289	0.0302	0.0316
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0337	0.0322	0.0308	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0293	0.0308	0.0322	0.0337
0.6826	0.7136	0.7476	0.7850	0.7059	0.6412	0.5874	0.5420	0.5030	0.4693	0.4399	0.4139	0.3908	0.3722	0.3552	0.3398
0.0354	0.0339	0.0323	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0308	0.0323	0.0339	0.0354
0.6501	0.6796	0.7120	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3722	0.3544	0.3383	0.3236
0.0371	0.0355	0.0339	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0322	0.0339	0.0355	0.0371
0.6205	0.6488	0.6796	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3552	0.3383	0.3229	0.3089
0.0388	0.0371	0.0354	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0337	0.0354	0.0371	0.0388
0.5936	0.6205	0.6501	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3398	0.3236	0.3089	0.2955

Figure 5. Evaluation set for validation of parameterised PINN against the reference solver. The top value in each cell represents the absorption cross-section, Σ_a , while the bottom value represents the diffusion coefficient, D .

3.2.1. PINNs architecture and training configurations

For the parameterisation study, the model architecture consisted of three inputs, four hidden layers, and one output, with layer widths $3 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 64 \rightarrow 1$ and a tanh activation functions. Training minimised the mean-squared PDE residual using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of 10^{-4} for 100,000 epochs. The model was trained using 10,000 randomly spaced collocation points. The training was completed in 14.52 minutes on an M4 MacBook Pro using PyTorch with Apple's Metal (MPS) backend.

3.2.2. Parameterisation Within Range

Figure 6 shows the error metric for Case 1, where both (Σ_a, D) lie within the training bounds. The maximum relative difference is 0.66%, with a maximum RMSE of 6.57×10^{-3} , and a maximum absolute error of 1.4×10^{-2} relative to the finite difference solver. The largest errors occur near the lower right corner regions of the sampled parameters space. This is consistent with limited training coverage near the boundaries when parameters are drawn randomly, which may have left the corners sparsely populated. Uniformly generated points, or Latin hypercube sampling, would provide improved coverage and may reduce there errors.

Figure 6. 1D PINNs solution compared with the reference finite difference solver

3.2.3. Parameterisation Outside Range

Figure 7 presents Case 2 with (Σ_a, D) outside the training bounds. As expected for extrapolation, the errors increase relative to Case 1. The maximum relative difference rises to 1.90%, with a maximum RMSE of 3.87×10^{-2} and a maximum absolute error of 1.4×10^{-2} . However, the mean relative difference remained low at 0.47% compared to 0.39% for case 1, indicating that the out of range points are still predicted accurately. This indicates that the learning mapping $\phi(x; \Sigma_a, D)$ varies smoothly with the parameters and generalise with small increases in error. The largest difference is again in the lower right hand corner which suggest the model seems to predict better with larger parameter values.

Figure 7. 1D PINNs solution compared with the reference finite difference solver

3.2.4. Computational Times

After training, simulations were carried out on 1000 parameter randomly generated pairs of (Σ_a, D) . The total PINN prediction time was 0.7 seconds, whereas the finite difference solver took 27.6 minutes without any graphical outputs. This corresponded to a speed improvement of approximately $\times 2365$ for the geometry considered.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary study presented here demonstrates that, once trained, PINNs can generate fast and accurate solutions for unseen material properties without retraining. For the within range evaluation, the model showed strong agreement with the reference finite difference solution across the trained parameter space, with only minor error increases near the edges of the sampled domain. For the out of range evaluation, the model also generalised beyond the training bounds, maintain low errors even when the

material parameters were perturbed by 15% outside the sampled range. Expectedly, the largest discrepancies occurred near the parameter space boundaries where the training coverage was the weakest. Further reductions in both peak and boundary related errors are expected through hyperparameter tuning. These include adjustments to the number and distribution of collocation points, weights of the loss function, configuring network depth and width. As robustness improves, PINNs offer a mesh-free alternative for reactor neutronics, with the additional advantage that a single trained model can be reused across material variation without rerunning a full numerical solver for each new parameter set. Finally, this work is intended as a feasibility demonstration of parameterised PINNs in a deliberately simplified settings. Extending to reactor-relevant problems introduces a higher-dimensional input space (eigenvalue problems, multi-group constants, spatial heterogeneities, burn up/thermal hydraulic feedback) and may require additional strategies to avoid prohibitive training costs associated with the curse of dimensionality. Future work will address these challenges using structured parameterisation, domain decomposition for heterogenous geometries and adaptive sampling strategies, possibly complemented with limited data to guide the training in the most informative regions of the parameter space.

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